

Extend. Expand. Exemplify.

The SGCI team continues to offer its services AND brings you a new Center of Excellence to Extend Access, Expand the Community, and Exemplify Good Practices for CI through Science Gateways.

Impact of (Geo)AI on National Compute Resources

Michael Zentner
Division Director, Sustainable Scientific Software
Director, SGX3 Center of Excellence for Science Gateways
San Diego Supercomputer Center
University of California, San Diego

NSF awards
1547611
2231406

The NSF-Funded Center of
Excellence for Science Gateways

- Consulting Services
 - UX
 - Architecture
 - Gap Analysis
 - Sustainability
 - Science Gateway Construction and Operation
- Community Building
 - Workforce Development
 - Conference (Pittsburgh October 30-November 1)
 - Sustainability Focus Week & Jumpstart (September 12-14)
 - Domain Specific Roadshow
- Suggesting the Future – Blueprint Factories
- help@sciencegateways.org

Schrödinger

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V \psi$$

Schrödinger

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V \psi$$

Just how
many
people do
this?

700+ Simulation Tools
~1,000,000 Simulations Annually

So What?

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So What?

So What?

So What?

SGX3

SGCI

So What?

So What?

So What?

So What? (Relevance to Geo)

Where should I
deploy firefighters?

This field is showing
stress, what now?

How high will the
storm surge be?

Is that a methane
leak in my pipeline?

So What?

So What?

Conversations with Data and Models!

So What?

Conversations = Understanding

BUT WAIT

THERE'S MORE

**Science Gateways
are engines of
Broader Impact...**

**...because they democratize
access and engage large,
diverse audiences.**

Science Gateways are sustainability habitats for scientific applications, scientific data sets, their creators, their users...

...because they are places many can pool together to address sustainability as a group.

Science Gateways also can capture the scientific process for provenance and reproducibility AND for analysis by AI to assist in scientific discovery!

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